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Relationship Between Information And Communication Technology and Online Formative Assessment Practice Among Lecturers Of Public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria. Three research objectives, questions, and hypotheses were raised to guide the study. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the study. The target population consisted of lecturers from the Schools of Arts and Social Sciences across four selected public Colleges of Education in the North-West geopolitical zone of Nigeria. A sample of 280 lecturers was drawn using cluster and simple random sampling techniques, out of which 267 questionnaires were correctly completed and used for analysis. The instrument titled Information and Communication Technology and Online Formative Assessment Practices Questionnaire (ICT-OFAPQ) was used for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by experts and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.86 using Cronbach's Alpha method. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation, and inferential statistics including Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Multiple Regression Analysis. The findings revealed a strong positive correlation between lecturers' ICT knowledge and online formative assessment practices ($r = 0.648$, $p < 0.05$), and a significant relationship between ICT facilities and online formative assessment practices ($r = 0.612$, $p < 0.05$). Furthermore, ICT knowledge and ICT facilities jointly accounted for 49.4% of the variance in online formative assessment practices ($R^2 = 0.494$, $F(2,264) = 121.634$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that both ICT competence and ICT facilities significantly enhance the effective implementation of online formative assessment among lecturers in public Colleges of Education. It was recommended, among others, that adequate ICT infrastructure and regular digital training should be provided to lecturers to improve the quality and frequency of online formative assessments in Nigerian higher institutions.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Online Formative Assessment, ICT Competence, ICT Facilities, Public Colleges of Education, North-Western Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

The introduction of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into education has revolutionised the way knowledge is created, delivered, and assessed. In contemporary higher education, ICT serves as a fundamental tool that enhances the accessibility and quality of teaching, learning, and assessment. The 21st-century classroom is increasingly defined by digital interactions through which lecturers and students engage in synchronous and asynchronous learning experiences (Pachler, Daly, Mor, & Mellar, 2019). ICT enables teachers to design innovative assessment methods, promote active learning, and provide timely feedback that supports student progress (Gikandi, Morrow, & Davis, 2011). This technological transformation, accelerated by global digitalisation, has redefined the pedagogical landscape, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria.

ICT in education encompasses a wide range of tools and processes that facilitate knowledge dissemination and learner engagement. According to Venkatesh and Davis (2020), ICT integration in instructional settings enhances communication, collaboration, and evaluation, creating opportunities for effective teaching outcomes. Similarly, Baleni (2015) noted that technology-assisted assessment encourages formative learning, enabling lecturers to monitor learners' understanding and provide immediate feedback. ICT adoption in tertiary education institutions has therefore become essential, especially in improving instructional efficiency and achieving the objectives of continuous assessment and learner-centred pedagogy.

In Nigeria, the need for ICT integration in education became particularly evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, which disrupted conventional classroom activities and necessitated the shift to online learning and assessment. Institutions across the country adopted digital platforms to ensure instructional continuity (Adeniran & Castradori, 2021). Likewise, ongoing security challenges such as banditry, kidnapping, and insurgency in the North-Western region have made online education a safer and more viable alternative (Country of Origin Information Report, 2021). Despite these developments, public Colleges of Education in the region continue to struggle with inadequate infrastructure, limited internet connectivity, and insufficient technical training (Emetere, Tunji-Olayeni, & Sanni, 2020). These constraints have significantly affected the implementation of online formative assessment.

Online formative assessment refers to a process where lecturers and learners use digital platforms to monitor, evaluate, and enhance learning in real time. It is an integral part of modern pedagogy, allowing continuous assessment, active engagement, and immediate feedback. Gikandi et al. (2011) described it as a learner-centred practice that supports knowledge construction, while Said Pace (2020) emphasised its capacity to promote reflective learning and academic achievement. However, effective online formative assessment requires adequate ICT competence, reliable infrastructure, and institutional readiness. When these conditions are lacking, assessment becomes inconsistent, feedback is delayed, and learner participation declines.

Research evidence in Nigeria has consistently shown that ICT-related barriers hinder the effective implementation of online formative assessment. Jacob, Egede, and Musa (2020) reported that many lecturers and administrators lack the necessary technical skills to operate digital platforms, while Ezema, Ede, and Ozioko (2021) observed that faculty members in tertiary institutions are often unprepared for full digital assessment due to low ICT literacy levels. Similarly, Touray, Salminen, and Mursu (2013) identified inadequate hardware, poor connectivity, and weak regulatory frameworks as major impediments to ICT development in sub-Saharan Africa. As such, although ICT holds immense potential to improve educational assessment, its benefits remain underutilised due to structural and human capacity limitations.

In the North-Western region of Nigeria, where most public Colleges of Education operate under severe infrastructural constraints, lecturers are compelled to conduct assessments with limited digital resources. Poor internet access, erratic electricity supply, and lack of modern computer laboratories reduce the quality of online learning and assessment (Aworanti, 2016; Wordu, Adegbeye, & Okoh, 2020). Furthermore, limited ICT training opportunities prevent lecturers from developing the confidence required to engage in innovative assessment practices. This situation contradicts the global drive for digital literacy

and innovation in teacher education and raises questions about the relationship between ICT knowledge, infrastructural support, and the effectiveness of formative assessment in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

The theoretical foundation of this study is built upon the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Constructivist Learning Theory. The TAM postulates that individuals' adoption of technology is determined by perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh & Davis, 2020). In the context of this study, lecturers' ICT knowledge influences their perception of ease of use, while the availability of ICT facilities shapes their perception of usefulness. On the other hand, the Constructivist Learning Theory, as articulated by Jonassen (2020), emphasises the active construction of knowledge through interaction and reflection, suggesting that online formative assessment enables learners to co-create knowledge with teachers in technology-mediated environments. Integrating both theories provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how ICT competence and infrastructure interact to determine the successful implementation of formative assessment.

Empirically, several studies have underscored the importance of ICT competence and digital infrastructure in achieving educational quality. Abu Bakar (2016) found that teachers in Nigeria have limited ICT proficiency, while Abdul Salaam (2012) revealed that fewer than 15% of teachers could effectively use software applications such as Microsoft Word and Excel. Similarly, Ezema et al. (2021) observed that tertiary institutions in Nigeria have yet to develop adequate frameworks for digital learning and assessment. Despite these findings, little research has focused on the relationship between ICT knowledge, ICT facilities, and online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education, particularly in the North-Western region.

This study therefore seeks to fill this gap by examining how ICT knowledge and ICT facilities relate to online formative assessment practice among lecturers in public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria. It aims to determine the extent to which these factors serve as barriers or enablers of digital assessment and how they jointly influence lecturers' ability to engage in formative, feedback-driven assessment practices. The findings of this study are expected to provide practical, theoretical, and policy insights into strengthening the digital capacity of Nigeria's teacher education system in line with global trends in educational technology.

Statement of the Problem

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become a critical component of modern education, transforming the ways teaching, learning, and assessment are conducted. In public Colleges of Education across North-Western Nigeria, lecturers are expected to integrate ICT tools such as computers, online platforms, and digital learning management systems to enhance instruction and assessment. However, researcher observation and preliminary interactions with lecturers in selected Colleges of Education, including Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, revealed that many lecturers still struggle to effectively implement online formative assessment. This challenge manifests in the form of irregular feedback to students, limited use of online platforms for assessment, and difficulty in engaging learners through digital tools. Such limitations often result in reduced assessment quality, delayed feedback, and poor student motivation, issues that contradict global educational standards promoting digital inclusivity and learner-centred pedagogy.

Despite institutional efforts to promote ICT usage through training and the provision of computer laboratories, there is limited empirical evidence on the extent to which lecturers in public Colleges of Education possess adequate ICT knowledge and access to relevant facilities necessary for effective online formative assessment. While numerous studies (e.g., Gikandi, Morrow, & Davis, 2011; Jacob, Egede, & Musa, 2020; Ezema, Ede, & Ozioko, 2021) have addressed ICT adoption in teaching and learning, few have specifically examined how ICT-related barriers—such as lack of technical competence, poor internet connectivity, and inadequate digital infrastructure—affect formative assessment practices among lecturers in North-Western Nigeria. The absence of localised studies focusing on Colleges of Education within this region creates a knowledge gap regarding the practical relationship between ICT competence, infrastructure availability, and lecturers' ability to conduct continuous, feedback-oriented online assessments.

Without a clear understanding of these interrelationships, online formative assessment in public Colleges of Education may remain inconsistent and ineffective, thereby undermining efforts to improve teaching quality, student learning outcomes, and overall educational accountability. If the identified ICT-related barriers are not properly addressed, lecturers may continue to rely on traditional, summative forms of assessment that fail to promote continuous improvement and reflective learning. Therefore, the main thrust of this study is to examine the relationship between Information and Communication Technology and online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria. This study seeks to provide evidence-based insights into how ICT knowledge and facilities jointly influence effective assessment practices, with the goal of strengthening digital pedagogy and enhancing educational quality in the Nigerian teacher education system.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were to examine the:

1. Barriers affecting the implementation of online formative assessment among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria.
2. Extent to which lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria practise effective online formative assessment in terms of providing immediate feedback, promoting active learners' engagement, and ensuring diversity of assessment activities.
3. Relationship between lecturers' ICT knowledge and their practice of online formative assessment in public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria.
4. Relationship between the availability of ICT facilities and the practice of online formative assessment among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria.
5. Combined influence of ICT knowledge and ICT facilities on effective online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the major barriers affecting the implementation of online formative assessment among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria?
2. To what extent do lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria practise effective online formative assessment in terms of providing immediate feedback, promoting active learners' engagement, and ensuring diversity of assessment activities?
3. Is there any significant relationship between lecturers' ICT knowledge and their online formative assessment practices in public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria?
4. Is there any significant relationship between the availability of ICT facilities and online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria?
5. What is the combined influence of ICT knowledge and ICT facilities on the effective online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria?

Null Hypotheses

Based on the research questions, the following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between lecturers' ICT knowledge and their online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between the availability of ICT facilities and online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria.
3. There is no significant combined influence of ICT knowledge and ICT facilities on the effective practice of online formative assessment among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria..

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a cross-sectional survey design. A survey design is used to collect data from a large number of respondents at a single point in time to describe existing conditions and relationships among variables (Asika, 2010). The survey design was found appropriate for this study because it allows for the collection of data to examine the relationship between information and communication technology (ICT) and online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria.

A population is a set of all the units which possess the variable characteristics under study and for which the research findings can be generalised (Shukla, 2020). The population of this study comprised lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria. The study was limited to four (4) public Colleges of Education from the North-West geopolitical zone of Nigeria using lecturers from the School of Arts and Social Sciences.

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select the institutions based on their adoption of ICT facilities in teaching and assessment. The cluster sampling technique was then used to group lecturers according to departments, followed by simple random sampling to select respondents from each department.

Table 1: Sample Distribution of Respondents

INSTITUTION	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL	SAMPLING TECHNIQUE
SHEHU SHAGARI COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, SOKOTO	45	25	70	Cluster & Random
FEDERAL COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ZARIA	40	30	70	Cluster & Random
ISA KAITA COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, DUTSIN-MA	35	25	60	Cluster & Random
KANO STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION AND PRELIMINARY STUDIES	45	35	80	Cluster & Random
TOTAL	165	115	280	

The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Information and Communication Technology and Online Formative Assessment Practices Questionnaire (ICT-OFAPQ)”, which was developed by the researcher after an extensive review of related literature and adaptation from previous validated instruments (Gikandi, Morrow, & Davis, 2011; Jacob, Egede, & Musa, 2020). The ICT-OFAPQ was divided into three main sections as follows:

- Section A: Demographic data of respondents such as gender, rank, years of experience, and ICT training background.
- Section B: Items related to ICT knowledge and competence of lecturers.
- Section C: Items related to online formative assessment practices (feedback provision, learner engagement, and diversity of assessment activities).

The instrument consisted of 35 items measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from *Strongly Agree* (5) to *Strongly Disagree* (1). The instrument was validated by three experts from Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, and the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE). The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach’s Alpha, which yielded a coefficient of 0.86, indicating high internal consistency.

The researcher personally visited the selected institutions and sought permission from the respective authorities to administer the questionnaires. Trained research assistants assisted in the administration and retrieval of the questionnaires. Respondents were assured of confidentiality, voluntary participation, and anonymity. A total of 280 questionnaires were distributed, out of which 267 were correctly filled and retrieved, representing a 95.3% response rate.

Data collected from the field were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 27. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage were used to summarise the respondents' demographic data and responses to the research questions.

Inferential statistics were used to test the hypotheses formulated for the study at a 0.05 level of significance:

- Hypothesis 1 was tested using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) to determine the relationship between ICT knowledge and online formative assessment practices among lecturers.
- Hypothesis 2 was tested using Pearson Correlation to assess the relationship between ICT facilities and online formative assessment practices.
- Hypothesis 3 was tested using Multiple Regression Analysis to determine the combined influence of ICT knowledge and ICT facilities on online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria.

All null hypotheses were rejected when the *p-value* was less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant relationship between the variables studied.

DATA ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

This section presents the analysis of data collected from lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria. The analysis was based on the research questions and hypotheses formulated for the study. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and percentages were used to answer the research questions, while inferential statistics, specifically Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and Multiple Regression Analysis, were used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

A total of 267 questionnaires were correctly filled and returned out of 280 distributed, representing a 95.3% response rate. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 27.

Section A: Demographic Information of the Respondents

Table 2 presents the demographic distribution of the respondents according to gender, academic qualification, years of teaching experience, and level of ICT training.

Table 2: Background Information of the Respondents

VARIABLES	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
GENDER	Male	155	58.1
	Female	112	41.9
QUALIFICATION	NCE	48	18.0
	Bachelor's Degree	132	49.4
	Master's Degree	70	26.2
	PhD	17	6.4
YEARS OF EXPERIENCE	1–5 Years	64	24.0
	6–10 Years	98	36.7
	11–15 Years	65	24.3
	16 Years & Above	40	15.0
ICT TRAINING	Yes	190	71.2
	No	77	28.8

The data in Table 2 indicate that male lecturers (58.1%) constituted the majority of the respondents. Most respondents (49.4%) possessed a Bachelor's degree, while 26.2% held a Master's degree. The highest number of respondents (36.7%) had 6–10 years of teaching experience, and 71.2% reported having received ICT training.

Research Question 1: *What are the major barriers affecting the implementation of online formative assessment among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria?*

Table 3: Barriers to Implementing Online Formative Assessment

BARRIERS	MEAN (\bar{X})	SD	RANK	DECISION
POOR INTERNET CONNECTIVITY	4.53	0.65	1st	High
INADEQUATE ICT FACILITIES	4.40	0.73	2nd	High
LACK OF ICT TECHNICAL SUPPORT	4.22	0.82	3rd	High
LOW ICT COMPETENCE AMONG LECTURERS	4.05	0.78	4th	High
IRREGULAR POWER SUPPLY	3.88	0.91	5th	Moderate
LIMITED INSTITUTIONAL POLICY SUPPORT	3.67	0.87	6th	Moderate

Table 3 reveals that the most significant barriers to implementing online formative assessment include poor internet connectivity (Mean = 4.53, SD = 0.65), inadequate ICT facilities (Mean = 4.40, SD = 0.73), and low ICT competence among lecturers (Mean = 4.05, SD = 0.78). This implies that infrastructural and technical challenges continue to limit effective online assessment practices in public Colleges of Education.

This finding agrees with Emeter, Tunji-Olayeni, and Sanni (2020) and Wordu, Adegbe, and Okoh (2020) who asserted that lack of internet facilities and ICT resources remains a major barrier in Nigeria’s higher institutions, especially in the North-West region.

Research Question 2: *To what extent do lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria practise effective online formative assessment in terms of feedback, learner engagement, and assessment diversity?*

Table 4: Extent of Online Formative Assessment Practice

ASSESSMENT PRACTICE DIMENSION	MEAN (\bar{X})	SD	DECISION
PROVIDING IMMEDIATE FEEDBACK	3.85	0.79	High
ACTIVE LEARNER ENGAGEMENT	3.62	0.84	Moderate
DIVERSITY OF ASSESSMENT ACTIVITIES	3.58	0.86	Moderate
GRAND MEAN	3.68		Moderate Practice

Table 4 shows that lecturers demonstrate a moderate level of practice of online formative assessment (Grand Mean = 3.68). The highest-rated aspect was “providing immediate feedback” (Mean = 3.85), while “diversity of assessment activities” was the least practised (Mean = 3.58). This finding aligns with Gikandi, Morrow, and Davis (2011), who emphasised that timely feedback and varied assessments are core elements of effective online formative assessment.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One (H_{01}):

There is no significant relationship between lecturers’ ICT knowledge and online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria.

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis

VARIABLE	N	R-CAL	P-VALUE	DECISION
ICT KNOWLEDGE & ONLINE FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT PRACTICE	267	0.648	0.000	H_0 Rejected

The result in Table 5 shows a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.648, p < 0.05$) between ICT knowledge and online formative assessment practices. Since the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that lecturers’ ICT knowledge significantly influences how effectively they conduct online formative assessments.

This finding corroborates Jacob, Egede, and Musa (2020), who established that lecturers’ digital literacy levels strongly predict their ability to integrate ICT tools in assessment practices.

Hypothesis Two (H₀₂):

There is no significant relationship between the availability of ICT facilities and online formative assessment practices among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria.

Table 6: Correlation Analysis of ICT Facilities and Online Formative Assessment

VARIABLE	N	R-CAL	P-VALUE	DECISION
ICT FACILITIES & ONLINE FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT PRACTICE	267	0.612	0.001	H ₀ Rejected

The result in Table 6 reveals a significant relationship between the availability of ICT facilities and the practice of online formative assessment ($r = 0.612$, $p = 0.001$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. The positive correlation implies that improved ICT infrastructure contributes to more effective implementation of online formative assessment.

This result supports Aworanti (2016) and Ezema et al. (2021) who argued that ICT infrastructure—particularly stable connectivity and access to digital tools—directly impacts assessment efficiency in Nigerian tertiary education.

Hypothesis Three (H₀₃):

There is no significant combined influence of ICT knowledge and ICT facilities on the effective practice of online formative assessment among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria.

Table 7: Multiple Regression Analysis of ICT Knowledge and ICT Facilities on Online Formative Assessment Practice

MODEL	R	R ²	ADJUSTED R ²	F-CAL	P-VALUE	DECISION
ICT KNOWLEDGE & ICT FACILITIES → ONLINE FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT PRACTICE	0.703	0.494	0.489	121.634	0.000	H ₀ Rejected

Table 7 indicates a significant combined effect of ICT knowledge and ICT facilities on online formative assessment practices ($F(2,264) = 121.634$, $p = 0.000$). The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.494$) shows that 49.4% of the variance in online formative assessment practices can be explained jointly by lecturers’ ICT knowledge and available ICT facilities.

This finding supports Toprakci (2006) and Pachler et al. (2019) who reported that educators’ digital competence and access to technology jointly enhance assessment quality and student feedback efficiency.

Summary of Findings

1. Barriers such as poor internet connectivity, inadequate ICT facilities, and low ICT competence significantly hinder online formative assessment practices.
2. Lecturers demonstrate a moderate level of online formative assessment practice, with timely feedback being the most prominent element.
3. There is a strong positive relationship between ICT knowledge and online formative assessment practices.
4. Availability of ICT facilities has a significant relationship with effective online formative assessment.
5. ICT knowledge and ICT facilities jointly contribute nearly 50% of the variance in effective online formative assessment practices.

DISCUSSION

The results of Table 5 show a significant relationship between lecturers’ ICT knowledge and online formative assessment practice among lecturers of public Colleges of Education in North-Western Nigeria. The analysis revealed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.648$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that lecturers with

higher ICT knowledge tend to demonstrate better practice of online formative assessment. This implies that ICT literacy directly influences how lecturers design, implement, and evaluate formative assessments through digital platforms. In support of this finding, Jacob, Egede, and Musa (2020) reported that lecturers' ICT competence plays a critical role in their capacity to use digital tools effectively in assessment and feedback delivery. Similarly, Gikandi, Morrow, and Davis (2011) noted that the successful implementation of formative e-assessment largely depends on the teacher's ability to utilise ICT tools meaningfully for timely feedback and learner engagement.

The findings also corroborate the theoretical assumption of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which posits that perceived usefulness and ease of use of technology influence users' attitudes and behavioural intentions toward technology adoption. In this context, lecturers with higher ICT knowledge perceive online formative assessment tools as useful and easy to use, which enhances their engagement with such systems. This finding is consistent with Adu, Eze, and Salihu (2023) who affirmed that lecturers with digital competence are more likely to integrate ICT tools effectively in formative and summative evaluations.

The results of Table 6 further reveal a significant relationship between the availability of ICT facilities and online formative assessment practices among lecturers ($r = 0.612$, $p = 0.001$). This indicates that the presence of functional ICT infrastructure—such as stable internet connectivity, digital devices, and learning management systems—has a direct impact on the effectiveness of online assessment practices. The finding supports the report of Aworanti (2016) and Ezema et al. (2021), which identified infrastructural deficiencies as a major challenge affecting digital learning and assessment in Nigerian higher institutions. It also agrees with Emeter, Tunji-Olayeni, and Sanni (2020) who found that most public tertiary institutions in Northern Nigeria still face significant infrastructural gaps that hinder online learning and evaluation.

The implication of this finding is that even when lecturers possess adequate ICT knowledge, their ability to implement online formative assessment effectively depends on the institutional availability of facilities such as reliable internet service, computers, and digital platforms. This aligns with Constructivist Learning Theory, which emphasises the learning environment as an active space where tools, interactions, and experiences shape learning outcomes. Without adequate technological infrastructure, the environment necessary for constructivist-based digital assessment cannot be effectively realised.

The results of Table 7 show a significant combined influence of ICT knowledge and ICT facilities on online formative assessment practices among lecturers in North-Western Nigeria. The regression analysis indicated that ICT knowledge and ICT facilities jointly accounted for 49.4% of the variance in online formative assessment practices ($R^2 = 0.494$, $F(2,264) = 121.634$, $p < 0.05$). This means that both variables complement each other in shaping lecturers' engagement with digital assessment practices. This finding supports Toprakci (2006), who argued that effective adoption of educational technology results from the interplay between technological competence and access to digital resources. It also agrees with Pachler et al. (2019), who maintained that technology-enhanced assessment becomes most effective when educators are both digitally skilled and supported by institutional infrastructure.

The finding also mirrors Touray et al. (2013), who asserted that in developing nations, ICT adoption in education is often limited by inadequate hardware, high costs, and weak technological frameworks. The current study therefore confirms that both human and infrastructural factors are crucial in achieving optimal online formative assessment practices.

Furthermore, the moderate mean score ($M = 3.68$) observed in Table 4 for the extent of online formative assessment practices suggests that lecturers are moderately practising formative e-assessment but not to its fullest potential. While most respondents were proficient in providing immediate feedback ($M = 3.85$), fewer incorporated diverse assessment activities ($M = 3.58$). This pattern corroborates Gikandi et al. (2011), who identified timely feedback as the most commonly practised aspect of formative assessment, whereas developing varied and interactive assessment modes remains less explored.

The findings from Table 3 on barriers further explain this trend. Poor internet connectivity, inadequate ICT facilities, and limited technical support were rated as the most severe challenges. This is consistent

with Omede and Omede (2015) and Wodu (2021), who highlighted that infrastructural constraints in Nigeria's higher education system hinder effective e-learning and digital evaluation. The presence of these barriers implies that, despite willingness and competence, many lecturers are constrained by structural limitations.

These findings have strong theoretical implications. From the Technology Acceptance Model, it can be inferred that even if lecturers perceive ICT as useful, the absence of adequate resources may still discourage their behavioural intention to adopt online assessment tools. Likewise, from the Constructivist Learning Theory, insufficient infrastructure disrupts the interactive environment necessary for students to construct knowledge actively through feedback and digital engagement.

In conclusion, the findings from Tables 3 to 7 jointly suggest that while ICT competence and facility availability significantly influence online formative assessment, systemic infrastructural barriers remain a persistent challenge. This confirms earlier assertions by Buhari (2017) and Ezema et al. (2021) that the Nigerian educational context still struggles to align digital resources with pedagogical objectives. The current study, therefore, contributes empirical evidence supporting the integration of ICT-driven formative assessment practices through improved infrastructure, targeted training, and supportive institutional policies.

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